

Welcome to our HYBRIS' second newsletter!

Funded by the European Union, HYBRIS is a Horizon 2020 project involving 15 partners spread across 6 countries for a 3 year long series of developments to achieve a new generation of battery-based hybrid storage solutions for smarter, sustainable and more energy efficient grids and behind-the-meter systems.

At HYBRIS, we know that high-quality and technologically innovative batteries are key to reach the goals of the European Green Deal and contribute to the zero-pollution ambition set in it.

PROJECT NEWS

WHY IS HIL TESTING CRITICAL FOR NEXT GENERATION BATTERY SYSTEMS?

Coupling a battery energy storage (BESS) converter controller with a real-time simulation helps speed up development and optimize the design and service offerings in order to comply with certification and standards, such as grid codes. Learn more about the hardware-in-the-loop testing developed by Typhoon HIL.

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HIGH-LEVEL CONCEPT OF THE HYBRID ENERGY STORAGE

Brief description of the hybridization of energy storage system in HYBRIS project which stays for the combination of two different electrochemical storing technologies with different nature; one meant for peak power management and the other one for large storage of energy.

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THE POTENTIAL OF ECO-DESIGN TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE ENERGY STORAGE SYSTEMS

A short introduction to the preliminary assessment of system's sustainability, recyclability and materials safety through a detailed snapshot of current battery partners' technologies and a thorough review of the state-of-the-art to activate an eco-design strategy fostering further design steps in a superior sustainability framework.

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HESSTEC ADVANCED BATTERY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM HYBRID APPROACH

HESSTec provides a hardware and software control platform integrating proprietary algorithms oriented towards an optimal planning and multi-service operation by the end-user based on a deep know-how of the storage technologies and their performance into real grid scale applications. This battery energy storage system is thought for hybrid energy storage systems.

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KEMIWATT'S AQUEOUS ORGANIC REDOX FLOW BATTERY (AORFB)

The French company Kemiwatt is developing its technology of Aqueous Organic Redox Flow Battery where chemical energy is provided by two chemical components dissolved in liquids to form electrolytes. In this article, Kemiwatt explains the main advantages of this technology and its suitability for a wide range of energy services and stationary applications.

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PROJECT EVENTS

HYBRIS TOGETHER WITH THE FLORES NETWORK AT THE IFBB

Kemiwatt on behalf of HYBRIS participated at the FLORES – Network of Flow Battery Research Initiatives stand at the International Flow Battery Forum held in Brussels on June 28 & 29. Representatives from other four European research projects members of the FLORES Network were also at the stand (HyFlow, HIGREEW, BALIHT and SONAR).

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HYBRIS 3RD GENERAL ASSEMBLY

Finally, after 18 months on-board, HYBRIS partners could meet in-person during the 3rd General Assembly held last June 21st and 22nd held in Messina (Italy). It was also possible to visit the Italian pilot site located in Messina and the CNR-ITAE labs. The HYBRIS team presented major achievements and progress done so far.

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FIRST HYBRIS WORKSHOP ON ENERGY STORAGE AND ITS CRUCIAL ROLE IN THE ENERGY TRANSITION

The first HYBRIS Workshop took place on 23rd June 2023. The event was held by SAE and CNR-ITAE in Messina (Italy) and it was also available online via Zoom. This first workshop was organized by HYBRIS partners who presented the main features of the HYBRIS batteries' technologies and progress so far, and it was mainly addressed to the energy storage systems research community.

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HYBRIS AT THE ELECTRIMACS 2022 CONFERENCE

On May 18th, CNR-ITAE presented 'Numerical assessment of cooling systems for thermal management of lithium-ion batteries' at the ELECTRIMACS 2022 Conference, focused on the thermal management of batteries, work performed in the framework of the HYBRIS project.

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SECOND VIRTUAL GENERAL ASSEMBLY 24-25 JANUARY 2022

In January 2022, the 2nd General Assembly took place online. Main progress and challenges faced were presented by different partners and the consortium started planning the demonstration phase of the enhanced hybrid energy storage system. It was also presented the idea of the containerized solution which will embed the hybrid energy storage.

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PROJECT PUBLICATIONS

WPI MAIN OUTCOMES

Overall Requirements and Specifications

This report collects the requirements and specifications of each single battery technology used in HYBRIS, provides details on ICT and interoperability of the technologies investigated and useful information for the battery and hybrid energy storage system design.

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Levelized Cost of Storage (LCOS) Analysis

A general comparative analysis with different current hybrid energy storage technologies is performed in order to provide a preliminary overview of the project feasibility and show a major efficiency of the HYBRIS prototype.

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WP2 MAIN OUTCOMES

High-Level Concept of the Hybrid Energy Storage and the Requirements of Each Technology

This report collects the requirements and specifications of each single battery technology used in HYBRIS, provides details on ICT and interoperability of the technologies investigated and useful information for the battery and hybrid energy storage system design.

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WP7 MAIN OUTCOMES

Standardisation Landscape and Applicable Standards

This report contains the fields of interest related to HYBRIS project, identification and analysis of the standardisation technical committees related with the project as well as of the published standards and standards under development that can be useful and relevant for the project activities.

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1st HYBRIS WORKSHOP VIDEOS

EERA JP Energy Storage and Stories project

How EERA is promoting hybrid energy storage systems and how important holistic projects are to make these solutions feasible.

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Overall view of the HYBRIS project

Brief introduction to the HYBRIS concept and project goals.

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Messina pilot introduction

The Italian pilot use case and its goals focused on reaching high efficiency in a residential area where social justice meets scientific research.

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Aqueous Organic Redox Flow Batteries

Aqueous Organic Redox Flow Batteries is one of the battery technologies used in the hybridisation system developed in HYBRIS. Kemiwatt explains its advantages and applications.

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Member of the FLORES Network

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